

ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Trans-Border Closure: Implications on United Nations-ECOWAS Partnership

Madumelu .H.C. Madubueze¹, Obioma Davison Mbanefo², Emmanuel Omoniyi Awe³ & A. E. Oturuhoyi PhD⁴

^{1&2}Department of Public Administration, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria. mh.madubueze@coou.edu.ng ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5993-1406>; od.mbanefo@coou.edu.ng ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3117-6200>

³Department of Economics, Nile university of Nigeria, emmanuel.awe@nileuniversity.edu.ng
+2348065012286

⁴Legal Practitioner and Associate Lecturer, Department of Law, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State
oturuhoyiae@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study focused on strengthening UN – ECOWAS partnership towards sustaining Ecowas protocol on free movement of trades and persons. Consequently, the paper posit that the cardinal objective of Ecowas protocol which is to strengthen the economy of member states have suffered setback of recent as characterize by national security infriction as argued by some member states; this has led to Trans – Border closure. In this context, the paper examined national security as the object of Trans – Border closure. Flowing from this, the paper extracts the UN – Ecowas partnership to strive for better Trans-border relationships. The paper also examined the constitutive and apparent growing concern on the increased closure of Trans-Borders on the ECOWAS region. To investigate this, the study made use of qualitative research method. Data for the study were collected through secondary sources. The study is anchored on Liberal Intergovernmentalism theory. The paper raised a host of questions and also specifically examined issues relating to: why the growing trend in Trans – Border closure in Ecowas region? What is the implication of national security on Trans – Border closure? The challenges on UN – Ecowas partnership for a sustained Ecowas protocol. Finally, the paper concluded and made some policy prescriptions.

Key Words; ECOWAS, Protocol, Trans-Border Closure

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The United Nations since her establishment has continued to engage in partnerships, treaties and charters that promote global economic development and border security for the strengthening of world peace and global integration. Globally, many other regional organizations, in the bid to sustain their relationship with the United Nations, has on their own, established stronger security measures and trade liberalizations that will entrench brotherly co-existence and economic boom.

In Africa, we have the umbrella body which is the African Union. Beside the African Union, we have other regional bodies such as the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the Southern African Development Community, and Intergovernmental Authority on Development, East African Community, and Economic Community of Central African States etc. These regional bodies, made up of countries within a geographical spread. They are bonded by land borders which allow movement of persons and goods.

In the ECOWAS region, the protocols allows free movement of persons and trades for the same reasons as outlined and enshrined in the United Nations partnership laws and guidelines. The region have 15 member States which include; - Benin Republic, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, and Togo. The increasing trend in global interdependence has further strengthened the need and reasons for the establishment of the protocols amongst the regional organizations across Africa and ECOWAS in particular.

As noted by Adeola & Oluyemi (2012), the motivation for employment and better life inspired migration within the countries and across borders and so cities were attracted by migration from the rural areas while economically developed regions became magnets of migratory destinations. In West African countries such as Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, Senegal and Nigeria became destinations of international migration and Lagos and Dakar as preferred cities with teeming inflow of people from other parts of the sub-region. Nigeria which shares borders with francophone countries has to contend with influx of people from these countries and Lagos becomes the African metropolitan city for the citizens of these countries (Adeola & Oluyemi, 2012). To them, the economic boom of the 1970s and 80s brought about by the fortunes derived from the oil sector attracted increased immigrants to Nigeria from the sub-region. They added that, the Nigerian border which is porous became easy access especially as members of a single ethnic group hold dual nationalities.

In their submissions, because the movements were more of labour inspired, there was not much state reaction. However, Nigeria later started experiencing confrontations along the borders due to the activities of smugglers, traffickers and security challenges by the Muslim extremists who took the advantage of the porous borders to troop to the northern part of the country from Niger, Chad and northern Cameroon. At various times, some of these Muslim fundamentalists had declared holy war in the northern part of Nigeria. In the 90s for instance, the Maitasine Muslim fundamentalists and insurgency killed many innocent Nigerians before they were overwhelmed by the state security apparatuses (Adeola & Oluyemi, 2012).

The views explained by Adeola & Oluyemi (2012) cuts across the West African region and thus, after conceptual explanations, the paper focused on strengthening UN – ECOWAS partnership towards sustaining ECOWAS protocol on free movement of trades and persons by examining the national security as the object of Trans – Border closure. Flowing from this, the paper extracts the UN – ECOWAS partnership to strive for better Trans-border relationships and the constitutive and apparent growing concern on the increased closure of Trans-Borders on the ECOWAS region. To investigate this, the study made use of qualitative research method. The study is anchored on inter - governmentalism theory and finally make some policy prescriptions.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL EXPLANATIONS

2.1.1 Understanding the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement.

Aptly captured by Gondyi (2009), ECOWAS, a body consisting of 15 West African countries, was founded in 1975. It began with a modest mission the promotion of economic integration across the region, with a long-term vision of member states becoming a self-sufficient collective. Two of its critical components are the ECOWAS Commission and the ECOWAS Bank for Investment and Development; they work in the three common languages of the sub-region's citizens Portuguese, English and French. Divided into six parts with 13 articles, the Protocol A/P.1/5/79, Relating to Free Movement of Persons, Residence and Establishment draws its legality from the 1975 Treaty of the Economic Community of West African States (Gondyi, 2009).

Promulgated four years after the ECOWAS treaty, the Protocol was signed in Dakar to provide a legal framework for member states' citizens' right to enter, reside and engage in economic activities in the territory of other member states. For the implementation of the protocol, a three phase frame was adopted, to span over a 15-year period. Primarily, its purpose was to abolish visa and entry permit requirements, and to extend the right of residency and the right of establishment. It also grants member states' citizens the right to reside in another country in the sub-region for up to 90 days before obtaining permission for an extension of stay. The supplementary Protocol in 1985 included the right to seek and hold employment in host states in the region once the citizen had obtained an ECOWAS residence card or permit (Gondyi, 2009).

He noted that, In Article 4, member states are reserved the right to refuse admission into their territory any Citizens categorized as an inadmissible migrant under the country's law. Article 11 recognizes the potential need to expel individuals, and spells out the requirements for doing so. Ghana exploited this in 2012, when the country deported 12 Nigerian beggars; Ghana even slammed them with a fine of 12 Ghanaian Cedes (about 4USD). Expulsion, however, cannot

happen without first exhausting the provisions of other international instruments, like the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families. The penultimate article of the Protocol stipulates that the Protocol shall not affect more favourable provisions contained in agreements that have already been adopted between two or more member states (Gondyi, 2009).

According to Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun (2015), the ECOWAS Protocol on the Free Movement of People and Goods ensures free mobility of the community citizens i.e. citizens of member states. The Protocol on free movement conferred on Community citizens the right to enter and reside in the territory of any member state, provided they possessed a valid travel document and international health certificate (Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun, 2015). They noted that, it also allowed member states the right to refuse admission to any Community citizens who were inadmissible under the member state's own domestic law. The four supplementary protocols adapted between 1985 and 1990 committed member states, among other things, to: provide valid travel document to their citizens, grant Community citizens the right of residence for the purpose of seeking and carrying out income-earning employment, ensure appropriate treatment for persons being expelled, not to expel Community citizens en masse, limit the grounds for individual expulsion to reasons of national security, public order or morality, public health or non-fulfilment of an essential condition of residence (Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun, 2015).

They traced that, since the end of the Cold War, West Africa has been characterized by series of conflicts in different dimensions. There are hardly any of the countries in the sub-region which did not experience one form of crisis leading to conflict or another. Several authors such as Anadi (2005) and Olonisakin (2008) respectively, have tried to analyze the root causes of these conflicts and there is a consensus on a number of causes such as the weak structure of states inherited from colonial rule, unstable and feeble political institutions, under developed economy, mismanagement of natural resources, self-enriching rulers who will protect their stay in power by all means etc (Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun, 2015). Most of the states have experienced full scaled civil wars; examples are Liberia, Sierra Leone, Guinea Bissau, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, most have also experiences coup d'état, religious and ethnic clashes. There is no single factor that can be said to be the cause of any of these conflicts, however, our interest is not on the conflict and their causes per say, but in its implication for regional peace and security especially with the ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement as a point of analysis (Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun, 2015).

2.2 ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Growing Trends in Trans-Border Closure in West Africa.

As noted earlier, a careful study on the global peace today, reveals that nearly all regions across the world are having severe trans-border crimes of various degrees. Some of these crimes

involve human trafficking, terrorism, general boundary issues etc. Probably, that is why Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun (2015) observed that, looking at the nature of conflicts generally in Africa immediately after independence, conflicts were mostly over disputed territories e.g dispute over Ogaden between Ethiopia and Somalia, also between Nigeria and Cameroon over the Bakassi Peninsula, Libya and Chad over the Aouzou Strip, this went on for the most part of the Cold War period. However, from the end of the cold war, states started experiencing internal crisis as a result of a number of factors. One of which is the international criteria of democratization to receive foreign assistance coupled with civil unrest in their demands for more participation and openness in government. Thus, most West African states went through different dimensions of civil war (Opanike, Aduloju, Adenipekun, 2015).

Similarly, Okyere (2010) noted that, regional peace and security in West Africa has been under considerable attack from transnational organized criminal networks in recent years, with the resultant effect of devastating loss of lives, valuable properties and socio-economic consequences beyond measure. Drugs, arms and human trafficking, cyber-crime, money laundering and goods smuggling are highly prevalent across West Africa, with many States acting as both transit and destination points (Okyere, 2010). He concluded that, the region should empower independent security agencies with a mandate to combating organized crimes with a proactive role within the region. Their additional responsibility will be to create Community-based Suspicious Activity Reporting System to assist the national and regional frameworks. Such systems will augment collective responsibility to protect the region thereby prevent crime in all forms.

Again, is the issue of terrorism across the ECOWAS member States. It has brought about flagrant disobedience to ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement. Terrorism poses a serious threat to international peace, security and stability (ECOWAS-PDCPAT, 2008). It is a criminal act that undermines the pursuit of democracy, good governance and development, as well as the full enjoyment of human and people's rights. Attacks or even the threat of attack have far-reaching ramifications on trade, investment, tourism and the free movement of people, goods and services. It can also create or entrench social and cultural cleavages among people on either a racial or religious basis. Terrorism is therefore inimical to the noble aims and objectives of the Community, particularly the goals of promoting integration, economic development, peace, security and stability and raising the living standards of citizens in the Community, as enshrined in the Revised ECOWAS Treaty (ECOWAS-PDCPAT, 2008).

ECOWAS-PDCPAT (2008) also observed that, terrorist activities in the region have demonstrated the seriousness of the threat of terrorism to West Africa and the need for firm and sustained countermeasures. A number of Community Members have experienced various acts such as kidnapping and hostage-taking, hijacking, explosive bombing, gruesome and senseless murder and assassination, and other terrorist and mercenary attacks that have deprived citizens of the Community of their basic human rights, including the rights to life and freedom from fear. In

addition, citizens of the Community have been recruited into terrorist groups, which have committed atrocious acts around the world. Terrorism must therefore be categorically condemned and cannot, under whatever circumstances, be justified on any political, economic, social, ethnic, cultural, religious, ideological or health grounds (ECOWAS-PDCPAT, 2008).

2.2.3 Challenges of ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement and Implications on the UN – ECOWAS Partnership

The flagrant abuse of ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement of persons runs contrary to the basic ideals upon which the regional partnership with the United Nations were built. It is the desire of the United Nations that, regional organizations work together to ensure a right to free movement of persons. The objective of the United Nations towards this was to entrench economic growth and integration needed for global peace and cooperation. In pursuant to these very ideals to foster UN-ECOWAS partnerships, many Community Members have also entered into binding agreements at the international level, including the fourteen universal conventions and the four additional protocols, as well as various resolutions adopted by the United Nations (UN) General Assembly and the Security Council, most notably the landmark Security Council Resolution 1973 (2001) adopted under Chapter VII of the UN Charter, and the General Assembly Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy (2006), which provides for a global plan of action against terrorism (ECOWAS-PDCPAT, 2008).

Interestingly, in a recent survey conducted along selected borders in West Africa by the CLEEN Foundation in 2015. The study found that crossing the borders for many people is already an entrenched habit with most travellers reporting that they had crossed specific borders over 10 times. According to them, with four different supplementary Protocols ratified in 1985, 1986, 1989 and 1990, full implementation of the protocol remains slow; its full implementation remains a dream for the ECOWAS Commission and citizens in the sub-region (CLEEN Foundation, 2015) . They noted that, one of the biggest challenges of implementing the Protocol is that neither ECOWAS citizens nor State actors have a high level of awareness regarding the measures and their implications. Their findings indicate that, in all the Five Borders within the region, it is only in Nigeria and Benin that a clear majority of respondents were “aware” of the protocol. The table was shown below;

Table 1.1 Awareness of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement of persons among travellers

Responses	Mali-Cote d'Ivoire Border	Togo-Benin Border	Burkina Faso - Cote d'Ivoire Border	Nigeria-Benin Border	Ghana - Togo Border
Yes	47	30	48	80	49

No	53	70	52	20	51
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Sources: CLEEN Foundation Report, 2015

The implication according to them is that travellers are unaware of the rights and responsibilities set out in the protocol, and would be unable to challenge possible infringements by security agents and government officials. This low level of awareness is, in part, responsible for the reported expulsions of unwanted aliens (who are ECOWAS citizens), as well as targeted taxation and fiscal restrictions levied by some states.

The volatile nature of the sub-region is another core challenge inhibiting full implementation of the protocol (CLEEN Foundation, 2015). In 2003, *The Economist* described the West Africa's crisis, world's worst. The regional war has claimed perhaps half a million lives, and continues to blight millions more. Years of civil wars have left the region with countries focused on ensuring self-preservation first (The Economist, 2003). Predictably, this has been to the detriment of focusing attention on instruments of ECOWAS, and those of the African Union. For example, Cote d'Ivoire, one of the economic powerhouses of the region, battled with its own internal crisis for about five years; its recent peace only began in 2011. A list of recent regional crises include the Guinean clashes of 2013, the first and second Liberian civil wars, which ended in 2003, the ongoing conflict in northern Mali, the Tuareg rebellion in Niger, the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria, Niger and Chad, and the deadly, 11-year Sierra Leonean civil war. These conflicts are frequently fuelled by ethnic, religious, political and economic interests. Crises like these make deliberations about inter-state freedom of movement ineffectual, if not impossible (CLEEN Foundation, 2015).

Another challenge to the implementation of the Protocol is member states' lack of coordinated political will to monitor progress (CLEEN Foundation, 2015). Why citizens of member states err in the face of the law on this matter is simple; there is little to no awareness of the requirements for travel and work permits across borders. Where there is awareness, the process of procuring travel documents is fraught with different challenges, and there is no regionally sanctioned national identification process in West Africa. On the other hand, travel infrastructure, especially roads, are in bad conditions and grossly inadequate across the region. Officials on the border exploit travellers across the region, feasting on their ignorance and structural challenges (CLEEN Foundation, 2015).

The rights to refusal of admission as enshrined in the Protocol document, is also another challenge. Awumbila et al (2014) noted that, a major challenge to the implementation of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement is presented by the Protocol reserving to Member States the right to refuse admission into their territory, Community citizens deemed inadmissible under their domestic laws (Article 4). Affirming this, Adepoju et al. (2007) stated that, this provision undermines the purpose of the Protocol through the use of restrictive domestic inadmissibility laws. Some of the immigrants interviewed in both Sierra Leone and Ghana noted that border

management officials who want to force them to make unofficial payments tend to misapply this article which grants them the powers to refuse entry. This was probably why, Awumbila et al (2014), stated that, despite the existence of international agreements and national legal frameworks which prohibit discrimination, nationals of ECOWAS Member States are sometimes exposed to some forms of discrimination in both countries. Some privileges and rights are reserved for nationals and to which foreign nationals (including ECOWAS citizens) are not entitled to.

In Ghana, for instance, foreigners including nationals from ECOWAS Member States cannot work in sensitive security services. In both Sierra Leone and Ghana, public service jobs are only available to nationals and foreigners can only be employed in the public services under special arrangements. Those foreign nationals employed by governments in the civil service often provide either technical assistance or have been long-term residents of destination countries, or are granted permission under special executive arrangements (for example, bilateral agreements between the governments of Ghana and Sierra Leone). Even in the informal sector, there are some restrictions (Awumbila et al, 2014). As noted already, in principle migrants (including ECOWAS citizens) in both Sierra Leone and Ghana are only expected to be issued work permits in situations where there is no national for the same jobs. Both countries also have a quota system of issuing work permits which implies that some ECOWAS citizens may not get work permit even if they apply (Awumbila et al, 2014).

Nevertheless, the implications of these challenges are predicated on the backdrop of the fact that, the United Nations on their own right, has advocated for strengthening economic ties across regions globally and therefore, border-closures will not help in achieving that very goal. In affirmation, CLEEN Foundation (2015) noted that, closing the trans-borders of the region would be inimical to the principles of free movement. On the other hand, it is manifestly difficult to fence in a region which shares borders with volatile countries like Chad and Libya, complicated by the fact that the region has its own trouble spots.

Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Perspectives

This study is anchored on the Liberal Intergovernmentalism theory. Liberal intergovernmentalism is a political theory developed by Andrew Moravcsik in 1993 to explain European integration. The theory is based upon and has further developed

the Intergovernmentalist theory and offers a more authentic perspective than its predecessor with its inclusion of both neo-liberal and realist aspects in its theory. Generally, Intergovernmentalism treats states, and national governments in particular, as the primary actors in the integration process Moga (2009).

Intergovernmentalist approaches claim to be able to explain both periods of radical and converging governmental preferences and periods of inertia because of diverging national interests. Intergovernmentalism is distinguishable from realism and neorealism because of its recognition of the significance of institutionalization in international politics and the impact of domestic politics upon governmental preferences. Intergovernmentalism represents a way for limiting the conferral of powers upon supranational institutions, halting the emergence of common policies (Moga, 2009). In the current institutional system of the ECOWAS, the Council plays the role of the institutions which have the last word about decisions and policies of the Member States, institutionalizing a de facto intergovernmental control over Member States as a whole, with the possibility to give more power to a small group of states.

Liberal intergovernmentalism was created to be a grand theory. The theory seeks to explain the broader transformation of regional integration. Liberal Intergovernmentalist' theorists argue that it is impossible to explain the concept of the European Union with a single factor and believe that different approaches or theories are needed to genuinely understand the complexity of the EU. Liberal intergovernmentalism views states as the main actors, and sees the EU as an international institution that can be studied by viewing states as the main actors in a situation of anarchy, where each state achieves their goal through negotiations and bargaining. Liberal intergovernmentalism especially studies the process of these negotiations and bargaining between EU's member states (Cini & Perez, 2015).

Moravcsik in "The Choice for Europe" (1998) defines EU integration:

"EU integration can best be understood as a series of rational choices made by national leaders. These choices responded to constraints and opportunities stemming from the economic interests relative power of powerful domestic constituents, the of states stemming from asymmetrical interdependence, and the role of institutions in bolstering the credibility of interstate commitments" (Moravcsik, 1998).

This theory became suitable to study because, generally, Intergovernmentalism treats states and national governments in particular, as the primary actors in the integration process Moga (2009). Its approaches claim to be able to explain both periods of radical and converging governmental preferences. It is distinguishable from realism and neorealism because of its recognition of the

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4.1 Conclusion and Policy prescriptions

An extant literature indicates that, the ECOWAS region is yet to achieve her own set preferences on the Protocol on Free Movement and Migration. The policy still enjoys more rhetorics than action. This was why CLEEN Foundation in their 2015 report noted that, “when the Protocol on Free Movement and Migration was signed, the implementation period of 15 years was passed by 1994. Sadly, however, it is difficult to say that there is free movement of goods and persons within the region. When compared to the European Union, it pales into near insignificance. Nonetheless, the present visa-free travel system in 15 West African States is the largest free-movement corridor in Africa” (CLEEN Foundation, 2015).

Therefore, it is our firm argument that, for the ECOWAS body to achieve her set goals in pursuance to the ECOWAS-UN Partnership, the body has to revisit her 2020 vision of transforming into an “ECOWAS of People”. That objective is still achievable only when they shun corruption and sit-up to the very ideals and objectives that brought about the existence of the regional union.

We note that the ECOWAS body has done a lot in policy formulation through the available various policy frameworks. It is clear that the leadership of ECOWAS has all it takes to drive the organization forward. Thus, we suggest that, as the United Nations turns 75, we advocate for a special session of the UN-ECOWAS session to be held preferably in Nigeria, where the core issues on the Free Movement and Migration within the ECOWAS region will be discussed and followed pragmatically towards achieving that purpose. Clauses that made it difficult to operate such as rights given to member states to refuse admission into their territory and others should be revisited with a better policy option that will not make the policy counter-productive. If not followed this way, we are optimistic that, it’s all going to be rhetorics as usual and policies like “One Currency” project and all other related policies will never see the light of the day.

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Received: 5 November 2025

Revised: 8 November 2025

Accepted: 10 November 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.17583031](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17583031)

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